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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

CASCA members at Canadian Comprehensive Research Universities (CCRU) are in a unique situation with respect to research. These institutions are primarily undergraduate, with modest opportunities to supervise graduate students or post-doctoral fellows. Here we outline some of the main challenges faced by researchers at CCRU, as well as some of the, perhaps unexpected, advantages of being at a smaller institution.

In writing this article we fully appreciate the difference between research intensive universities and the CCRU universities. However, we strongly believe that CCRU universities are an integral part of the astronomy research landscape in Canada and continue to enable major research breakthroughs while providing notable student experiences. In this sense, perhaps diverging somewhat from perspectives espoused in much Canadian science policy commentary over the last five years, we view institutional diversity as actually a strength of Canadian astronomy rather than a weakness. We state without reservation that students should be accepted into Canadian astronomy from all backgrounds and institutions.

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1 Introduction

CASCA members at Canadian Comprehensive Research Universities (CCRU) are in a unique situation with respect to research. These institutions are primarily undergraduate, with modest opportunities to supervise graduate students or post-doctoral fellows. Here we outline some of the main challenges faced by researchers at CCRU, as well as some of the, perhaps unexpected, advantages of being at a smaller institution.

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2 Challenges of running a research program

2.1 Balancing Teaching and Research

At teaching-focused institutions, the expected course load for even researchers with significant NSERC support starts around five courses per year compared to the research-intensive expectation of three courses per year. This difference is further compounded by the fact that administrators at ACCRU institutions may be more reluctant to grant teaching releases for receiving external grants or participation on NSERC review panels.

However, trying to present a balanced assessment of the situation, the reality is that some ACCRU institutions are prepared to grant teaching releases on the basis of receiving major grant funding. Both Bishop's and Saint Mary's universities grant a course release per year over the period of an NSERC grant, while Mount Allison University grant a single course release which may be used at any time during the period of the grant.

2.2 Research Support

At small institutions, research offices are correspondingly small. This has both advantages and disadvantages. Although the staff is small, they can be very dedicated, and it is relatively easy to get personalized attention. Although the staff may not be familiar with all possible sources of funding, they are usually very willing to explore options and discuss possibilities.

With a small research office, internal deadlines are often informal and flexible, which can be a huge advantage. The staff are able to review grant applications before submission, and although they seldom have the subject matter expertise required to evaluate the proposal, they are very adept at finding peers who can read the proposal for comments. However, reflecting the nature of smaller institutions, it may not always be possible to find someone close enough in a given subject area to provide sub-field specific feedback, although, as noted, general feedback is almost always possible.

Another key deficit at smaller institutions is the lack of proposal development support for major grants. While larger institutions frequently have outside writing consultants contribute to the crafting and wording of major proposals, smaller institutions rarely have the resources to provide this support. Similarly larger institutions are often prepared to offer funds to highly regarded researchers to provide feedback on a proposal before it is submitted, a major advantage that researchers at smaller institutions do not have access to.

At small institutions, CFI programs can be under-subscribed, and it is possible to access the full institutional allocation. However, the allocations themselves are often smaller, and accessible funds can be limited. This can be alleviated by forming collaborations, effectively pooling the CFI allocation from several institutions.

2.2.1 The impact of research capacity development grants

One largely unappreciated funding program run by NSERC from 2003-2009 was the "Research Capacity Development in Small Universities" (RCDSU) program. Designed primarily as a seed-funding program, it provided small universities with sustained funding over a five-year period in the understanding that they would commit to continuing the funding outside of the five year window. In some sense it can be viewed as having similar goals as the UFA program in that it provided bridge funding for enabling growth in key areas.

The overall amounts on a per year basis provided by the program were comparatively modest in the context of research intensive universities. Per year contributions ranged from \$50k to \$150k. However, in the context of ACCRU universities that were struggling to provide research support through technicians the impact of this funding was significant. By bringing additional personnel funding in support of laboratory infrastructure the program helped significantly grow the profile of science research at a number of ACCRU institutions. In a very real sense for a number of institutions it increased the institutional profile of research significantly, and made central administrations look beyond the inherent high costs associated with science programs.

Aside from the need for observatories, it's also worth noting that while astronomy is not necessarily a strongly laboratory-reliant field, with the obvious exceptions of laboratory-based astrophysics and instrument laboratories, the overall profile of science within a given institution is an important component of supporting basic science like astronomy. Thus while astronomy itself was not explicitly a significant beneficiary of the RCDSU, it likely implicitly benefited greatly.

Over a decade later from when the program finished, it's worth asking the question could a small program like this have a similar impact today? Is it possible to bridge the participation of ACCRU institutions into even larger investments in science support, and thereby raise the profile of science internally at these institutions?

While it may sound like the job as already been done it's worth remembering that since the RCDSU finished professional programs have significantly grown in importance to universities, as have fees from foreign students. The profile of basic science in budgetary concerns is again on the wane. If there was ever a time to reinvigorate the profile of science within universities from a budgetary perspective, it is now.

3 HQP

3.1 Graduate Students

ACCRU institutions face a significant structural challenge in that many of their internal budgetary concerns are focused on funding associated with undergraduate students. Consequently, graduate students, and the research support structures they require, may be seen as something of a burden within institution unless there are compensating factors. Also, while these institutions may have exceptional researchers on campus, rarely does the combined output, which essentially is the determining factor in institutional research reputation, reach levels that impact public awareness and consequently recruitment.

Thus for smaller institutions the recruitment of graduate students falls largely on the preparedness of individual researchers to actively canvas their professional network for colleagues to recommend them students. While this route of recruitment exists for all universities, institutional reputation provides an accumulated advantage to those at larger research intensive universities. Consequently, set against the increasingly competitive nature of global research and the focus on Top500 lists for research, it is becoming increasingly difficult for ACCRU researchers to recruit graduate students. Of course, such competition concerns are felt by all universities with only the very top tier of world-wide research universities avoiding this issue, but for smaller universities the pressures are particularly acute.

3.2 Undergraduate Students

While ACCRU institutions face significant challenges in recruiting graduate students, at the undergraduate level there is less pressure and in some cases even advantages. A number of smaller teaching-oriented institutions have

strong reputations for their undergraduate experience and consequently, combined with some parents developing a strong focus on individual experience and small classes, leads to undergraduate cohorts with high capabilities.

At these institutions senior undergraduate students doing summer research or an honours thesis can provide a significant contribution to a research program. Ideally, students can be hired for two summers in addition to an honours thesis, giving them nearly as much time in a research group as a Masters student. However, undergraduates are much less experienced, and in some cases are missing essential background knowledge. Students need to be taught much of this background before they can make a reasonable contribution.

For the students, it is important to break the research program down into manageable chunks, such that the student can see progress and feel like they've accomplished something. Finding research problems that can be broken down like this can be challenging, and may rule out some more ambitious projects.

3.3 Tuition costs

The concern over tuition costs is ultimately shared across all universities in Canada, especially as graduate programs are increasingly compared against programs in other fields on an intra-institutional basis. Where departures occur is over the relative preparedness of institutions to offset costs by providing scholarships back to departments. The experience of ACCRU institutions is that there is an overwhelming bias toward remunerating departments that are perceived as professional e.g. Psychology, Finance, and in turn are perceived as a significant revenue stream for the institution. This inevitably reflects that fact that smaller institutions have smaller class sizes and are consequently disproportionately dependent on student fees. Thus while universities may adhere to incremental budgeting models, in practice program prioritization happens via fiscal redistribution.

Consequently, basic science departments, which inevitably have high costs associated with both teaching and research, are rarely rewarded internally and are largely viewed as a reputational cost-sinks by ACCRU institutions. This concern becomes especially acute for foreign students. While professional programs attract foreign students with means to pay significant funds, sometimes over well over double the domestic rates, the same cannot be said for astronomy students. Thus combined with the internal reluctance to return funds back to basic science departments as scholarships, and a view that supervisor NSERC funds can be leveraged to reduce central costs, the net effect is a diversion of federal research support to cover central administration costs.

It's worth noting such concerns are actually not unique to ACCRU institutions. The basic income unit equation for graduate student support varies from province to province, and researchers across Canada have different expectations for graduate student support. However, the harsh reality is that over the past five years the relative cost of foreign students has almost doubled at some ACCRU institutions. This has, in many cases, severely curtailed the possibility of supporting foreign students even for researchers with comparatively strong NSERC support.

At the root of this issue is how much support should an institution provide to a foreign graduate student? In effect this is set by the Canadian student visa requirements, that a student be able to demonstrate that they have at least \$10,000 plus the student fees in income. Some science programs at ACCRU institutions do not meet this requirement on the basis of support provided alone. One can only assume that students are being admitted on the basis of their family providing additional funds to overcome the limit. For professional programs that is likely a reasonable situation, for curiosity driven programs like astronomy that seems less appropriate.

3.4 Postdoctoral researchers

One of the single most important aspects of a vibrant research group is the presence of postdoctoral researchers. While care always needs to be taken to assure that these individuals do not end up becoming an inappropriate pool of labour that is not rewarded with requisite career progression possibilities, the reality is that individuals in these positions make exceptional contributions to the research accomplishments of many research groups.

The unfortunate fact for researchers at ACCRU institutions is that it can be extremely difficult to recruit and retain postdoctoral researchers. In effect impacting both the institutional and student (whether undergraduate or graduate) experience. While it is widely appreciated that NSERC Discovery Grant funds rarely provide sufficient

funding for postdoctoral researchers, the collaborative grants that do fund the bulk of these positions are rarely led by faculty at ACCRU institutions because the CFI and other budgets are so comparatively modest.

4 Research opportunities

4.1 Collaborations

One highly positive aspect of the astronomy community in Canada is that it is strongly inclusive. Many researchers at ACCRU institutions are directly involved in major national and international collaborations. Indeed, the only significant barrier to involvement of researchers from ACCRU institutions in major national/international developments is fiscal. For example, in the past few years there have been developments around supporting the JCMT under the operation of the EAO that required universities to provide fiscal support. Similarly involvement in the Canadian LSST Consortium has required that institutions provide significant internal funding to match sources provided by the Dunlap Institute. ACCRU institutions simply do not have the research support funds necessary to make participation in projects like these possible.

For all the strong inclusiveness of the national community, there are nonetheless reasons to be concerned about the future of the astronomy landscape in Canada. In particular there is growing movement towards "pay-to-play experiments" which collect a large data set and access is bought either monetarily or by contributions in-kind. This is distinct from the traditional astronomy observatory model, wherein science is assessed on its merits rather than fiscal/in-kind buy-in. This change in the operational behaviour of our field has the potential to create a significant divide between ACCRU institutions and the research intensive universities.

4.2 Pooling Resources

At small institutions, researchers are less likely to have peers at their own institute with whom they can jointly supervise and/or fund research personnel. However, co-supervision of graduate students by researchers at different institutes is possible, particularly if there is a shared graduate program and/or the possibility for researchers to obtain adjunct status at other institutes. Co-supervision of postdoctoral researchers is also possible, with two or more researchers from different institutes jointly funding these positions.

4.3 Streaming Colloquium Talks

Small institutions often don't have enough money to bring in colloquium speakers from other institutions. One way to still see excellent colloquium talks is to watch those at other institutions, either live-streamed or recently archived (a current list is hosted here: <https://www.astrobetter.com/wiki/Live+and+Archived+Astronomy+Talks>). Students can greatly benefit from this; watching a colloquium talk in a classroom with other students and a professor gives a very close approximation of colloquium talk at a larger institution. Holding a discussion immediately afterwards can help to make up for lack of direct interaction with the speaker. Further refinements may be to host remote colloquium talks, or even just a question-and-answer session with the speaker who presented a colloquium talk that was recently watched at the small institution. Another option is to encourage talks over Skype, reducing the need for travel.

5 Isolation

5.1 The Maple League

At ACCRU institutions, it is quite common to be the only astronomer in a physics department. As a result ACCRU researchers are isolated from the rest of the astronomical community. Special effort is required to maintain connections with the field and collaborators. However, isolation and geographical distance from potential collaborators is not a problem that is unique to astronomy. The Maple League was formed to help address some of these problems.

This is a collaboration between four small institutions (Bishop's, Mount Allison, Acadia, and St. Francis Xavier) which allows the institutions to share resources. In particular, the Maple League open courses offered at one campus to remote students on the other three campuses. This enables each institution to expand their course offerings, particularly the upper-level specialized courses. The Maple League also provides some funding for collaboration and meetings with researchers at other member institutions.

6 Key Points

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

Researchers at ACCRU institutions participate in cutting-edge research and international collaborations, and form an integral part of the astronomical landscape in Canada.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

N/A

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

CASCA should continue to lobby NSERC to support programs like RCDSU, which can encourage the research participation of ACCRU institutions not just in astronomy, but across the sciences.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

Researchers at small schools are often isolated from potential collaborators, both geographically and academically. Organizations like the Maple League help address these issues. Colloquium talks that are live-streamed or archived can also be beneficial, and larger institutions should be encouraged to make this available.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

Many ACCRU institutions have a strong reputation at the undergraduate level. This reputation attracts highly capable cohorts. These students are able to participate actively in research, and these programs can be an important tool in recruiting the next generation of astronomers.

6: In what ways is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

The cost of reinstating a program like NSERC's RCDSU would be relatively modest, but has the potential to greatly improve the profile of astronomy programs, and science more generally, at ACCRU institutions. The cost-benefit ratio is potentially very high across a wide range of fields.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

N/A

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

At smaller schools, it is common for undergraduates to be involved in research, providing a pool of excellent potential graduate students in astronomy. This is the start of training the next generation of astronomy.